

A New Mathematical Method for Dividing the Area of Land with a Trapezoidal Shape Longitudinally

Mohamed Karim Obaid , Mohammed A. Naser, Aula Hussein Ali Alobeidi, Mustafa A. Manshood
Agriculture College, Al-Muthanna University, Iraq

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Abstract:

Land with a trapezoidal shape is often divided by the attempt method. This research attempts to find a new way to divide this type of land by deriving a mathematical law. It can be applied to divide trapezoidal-shaped land into a number of shares of equal area, as well as equal degree of benefit from public services as much as possible.

Keywords: *land area, trapezoidal-shaped land calculation, mathematical law.*

Introduction

Calculating the land area alone is often not enough. Rather, the surveyor is tasked with dividing this area to meet a specific requirement. For example, dividing the land between a number of heirs. Allocating land for housing, agricultural and industrial investment, etc. Dividing the land into a number of shares must take into account the value of each share, as well as the total area of the land. This means that every share of the land benefits from public services such as irrigation and drainage canals, roads, and electricity and energy transmission lines equally with the rest of the shares. Therefore, there is no general law through which land can be divided, and it is not possible to limit the cases of land division as a result of the different areas and shapes of the lands and the degree of their benefit from the public services mentioned above. This context includes the trapezoidal-shaped land.

Land with a trapezoidal shape is often divided by the attempt method. Which includes choosing an approximate position for the division line, calculating the area of each share, and then

modifying this line if necessary. Taking into account the equality of these shares in the degree of benefit from public services (Al-Eishri, 2009). Therefore, this research attempts to find a new way to divide this type of land by deriving a mathematical law. It can be applied to divide trapezoidal-shaped land into a number of shares of equal area, as well as equal degree of benefit from public services as much as possible.

Materials and Methods

The field survey was conducted on the trapezoidal plot of land shown in Figure (1). It is located 23 kilometers north of the city of Al-Rumaitha in Al-Muthanna Governorate. For the period from 5 to 20 July 2021, as follows:

1 - Measuring the area of a plot of land using a measuring wheel according to the method described in Al-Maghrabi (2021). The directions and paths of the measuring lines were determined, and their straightness was controlled, using (3) Ranging poles, 2 meters long, Using the method mentioned in Al-Khifaf (2000). The locations of the points between which the distance was measured were marked

on the land using (10) wooden pegs, 30 centimeters long.

2 - Calculating the total area of the plot of land

The total area of the plot of land was calculated using the trapezoidal area law mentioned in cadastral calculation (2009). Shown below:

Area of a trapezoid = $[(\text{upper base} + \text{lower base})/2] \times (\text{height})$

3 - Calculate the percentage of error%

The percentage error between the actual area on the land of 5,200 square meters and the area calculated according to equations (1, 2) was calculated for each of the shares into which the land was divided Using the formula mentioned in Al-Subaihi (2008).

Percentage error% = $[(\text{actual area} - \text{calculated area}) / \text{actual area}] \times 100$

4 - Drawing the trapezoidal plot of land, the dimensions of which are shown in Figure (1). Using AutoCAD program. version 2009

The process of dividing the trapezoid-shaped land whose dimensions are shown in Figure (1) and drawn on a drawing scale of 1/1000 has been completed, by dividing it into 3 shares. The area of one share is equal to 1/3 of the total area of 15,600 square meters using the following equation:

$$X = \frac{2M}{HS} - \frac{M}{2(HS)} \quad (1)$$

X = location of the dividing line (Y) between the area of each share and the total area. On side (B) from side (D), which equals 65 meters, 65 meters, and 70 meters for the first, second, and third share, respectively.

M = The total area of the land is 15,600 Square meters. Which was calculated according to the law of the area of a trapezoidal shape, described in the cadastral calculation (2009) shown below.

$$M = \left(\frac{A+B}{2}\right) \times H$$

Where H = column length (height), which equals 120 meters.

S = the Number of shares or divisions which is equal to (3) shares.

$$W = \frac{M}{2(HS)} \quad (2)$$

W = location of the dividing line (Y) between the area of each share and the total area. On side (A) from side (D), which equals 21.666 meters, 21.666 meters, and 16.663 meters for the first, second, and third share, respectively.

Thus, the area of the shares (1, 2, 3) was calculated. Using the law of area of a trapezoid. With a percentage error of 0.00076%, according to the equation mentioned in Al-Subaihi (2008). As follows:-

First: Calculate the area of the share (1) (S₁), where

$$W = 21.666 \text{ meters}$$

$$X = 65 \text{ meters}$$

$$S_1 = \left(\frac{W+X}{2}\right) \times H$$

$$S_1 = \left(\frac{21.666\text{m}+65\text{m}}{2}\right) \times 120\text{m} = 5199.96\text{m}^2$$

Second: Calculating the area of share (2) (S₂), where

$$W = 21.666 \text{ meters}$$

$$X = 65 \text{ meters}$$

$$S_2 = \left(\frac{21.666\text{m}+65\text{m}}{2}\right) \times 120\text{m} = 5199.96\text{m}^2$$

Third: Calculating the area of the share (3)(S₃), where

$W = 60 \text{ meters} - (21.666 \text{ meters} + 21.666 \text{ meters}) = 16.668 \text{ meters}$

$X = 200 \text{ meters} - (65 \text{ meters} + 65 \text{ meters}) = 70 \text{ meters}$

$$S_3 = \left(\frac{16.668\text{m} + 70\text{m}}{2} \right) \times 120\text{m} = 5200.08\text{m}^2$$

Figure 1. Trapezoidal Plot of Land

Results and Discussion

First: Calculate the side (X) that represents the location of the dividing line (Y) Between the area of one share and the rest of the total area. On side (B) to the right side (on side D) as shown in Figure (2) using equation (1).

$$X = \frac{2M}{HS} - \frac{M}{2(HS)} \quad (1)$$

M = total area of the land

S = the number of shares into which the total area of the land is divided

H = Column length (height) of the plot of land to be divided

Second: Calculate the side (W) that represents the location of the dividing line (Y) Between the area of one share and the rest of the total area

On side (A) to the right side (on side D) as shown in Figure (2) using equation (2)

$$W = \frac{M}{2(HS)} \quad (2)$$

The equations (1, 2) can be proven using congruent triangles as follows according to Figure (2):

Figure 2. Trapezoidal Plot of Land

Let us assume that the total area of the land = M

Let us assume that the number of shares into which the total area of the land is divided = S

Thus, the area of one share = $\frac{M}{S}$

Let us assume that the area of one share is equal to the area of the triangle (QTN) So that:

$$\text{the area } \Delta QTN = \frac{M}{S}$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \times TN \times H = \frac{M}{S}$$

$$\frac{TN \times H}{2} = \frac{M}{S}$$

$$TN = \frac{2M}{HS} \quad (a)$$

Where (TN) represents the base of the triangle (QTN)

Let us also assume that the area of triangle QTR is equal to a quarter of the area of triangle QTN. This means that:

$$\text{The area } \Delta QTR = \frac{1}{4} \times \frac{M}{S} \quad \text{so that}$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \times TR \times H = \frac{1}{4} \times \frac{M}{S}$$

$$\frac{TR \times H}{2} = \frac{M}{4S}$$

$$TR = \frac{2M}{4HS} = \frac{M}{2HS} \quad (b)$$

Where (TR) represents the base of the triangle (QTR)

From Figure (2) it is noted that :

$$TN = TR + RN$$

$$RN = TN - TR$$

When replacing the values of TN and RN with equations (a, b). Considering that RN =X, the above equation becomes. as follows which is equation (1):

$$X = \frac{2M}{HS} - \frac{M}{2(HS)} \quad (1)$$

(X) represents the base of the triangle (QRN), whose area is equal to three-quarters of the area of the triangle (QTN), which is equal to the area of one share. This is because we assumed that the area of the triangle (QTR) is equal to a quarter of the area of the triangle (QTN). Therefore:-

$$\text{The area } \Delta QRN = \frac{3}{4} \times \frac{M}{S} = \frac{3M}{4S} \quad (c)$$

When drawing a straight line from point (T) to point (Z), as shown in Figure (2), we will get the triangle(QT'Z).

It is noted that the triangles(QTR) and (QT'Z) matches each other and equal in area. Therefore:

$$QZ = TR$$

When replacing the value of (TR) with equation (b). Considering that QZ =W , the above equation becomes as follows which is equation (2):

$$W = \frac{M}{2(HS)} \quad (2)$$

When we draw the straight line (Y) between the two points (R, Z), we will get the triangle (QRZ). It is noted from Figure (2) that the two triangles (QRZ) and (QT'Z) are congruent and equal in area, and both are equal to a quarter of the area of one share, and therefore:-

$$\text{The area } \Delta QRZ = \frac{1}{4} \times \frac{M}{S} = \frac{M}{4S} \quad (d)$$

When we add the area of the triangle (QRZ) to the area of the triangle (QRN), we will get the trapezoid (QZRN) whose area is equal to the area of one share and therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Area of a trapezoid (QZRN)} &= \\ \text{The area } \Delta QRZ + \text{The area } \Delta QRN &= \frac{M}{S} \end{aligned}$$

When replacing the area of the triangles (QRZ) and (QRN) with the equations (c, d)

$$\text{Area of a trapezoid (QZRN)} = \frac{3M}{4S} + \frac{M}{4S} = \frac{M}{S}$$

Where $\frac{M}{S}$ equals the area of one share

Thus, the area of one share will be in the shape of a trapezoid. Its upper base (QZ) is represented by the side (W). Its lower base (RN) is represented by the side (X). In addition to the dividing line (Y) that separates it from the rest of the total area of the plot of land. This is what is required.

Conclusion

The authors propose to use the method described in the article for the division of trapezoidal land.

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